

NUCLEATION AND CRACK GROWTH IN GRP UNDER STRESS CORROSION CONDITIONS

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Summary

A programmable photomicroscope for monitoring the accumulation and growth of the surface cracks which form under stress corrosion conditions is described. These surface cracks have been shown to maintain an approximate semi-circular shape so that the linear elastic fracture mechanics analysis for elliptical surface flaws can be used to calculate the stress intensity-crack growth rate curves. The rates of nucleation of stress corrosion cracks demonstrate significant differences between the performance of the epoxy and polyester glass fibre composites.

Introduction

The observation that E-glass fibre reinforced composites fail by stress corrosion cracking in an acidic environment has resulted in considerable research into the mechanism responsible. Of particular importance is the role of the matrix and how this influences the lifetime of the composite. It has been found that increasing the chemical resistance of the resin may not necessarily improve the stress corrosion resistance of the composite. In fact the performance is reported to be worse (1,2). Hogg (1) has attributed this effect to the lower fracture toughness of the more chemically resistant resins. Moreover, the work of Jones and Rock (3) has indicated that the integrity of the interface plays an important role.

A particular area of interest is the concept of a stress corrosion limit. That such a limit could exist is at first sight difficult to understand since E-glass fibres are particularly susceptible to acidic stress corrosion failure and the polymeric matrices are not expected to provide an impenetrable barrier to the aqueous acidic environment. The work of Aveston and Sillwood (4) suggested that a stress corrosion limit existed at crack growth rates below 10^{-8} ms⁻¹. Jones et al. (3) also postulated that a stress corrosion limit operated below initial applied strains of 0.35% for a particular isophthalic polyester resin based composite. In contrast, Hogg (1) and Jones et al (2) found no evidence for a stress corrosion limit in their polyester and epoxy resin composites respectively.

The nucleation of a stress corrosion crack appears to be by the failure of a single glass filament. The crack which is formed may or may not propagate through the surrounding resin depending upon the adhesion of the fibre to the matrix, the fracture toughness of the resin and the stress intensity at the crack tip. The initial slow propagation of this stress corrosion crack produces extremely planar fracture surfaces which are characterised by the mirror-like surfaces of the fractured glass fibres. With increasing crack velocity the fibre fracture surfaces show the development of river-lines, and at very high velocities, bifurcation occurs producing segments of glass fibre. The planar brittle crack formed in the initiation regions is amenable to analysis by linear elastic fracture mechanics. Price and Hull (5) and Aveston and Sillwood (4) have used double cantilever beam type specimens to obtain crack growth rates at varying stress intensities. A disadvantage of this type of test is that it does not produce any information about the rate of nucleation of these cracks.

We reported recently a method in which the growth of surface flaws could be used to determine the stress corrosion resistance of unidirectional composites (6). In the technique an area of the composite surface was monitored using a photomicroscope. The crack growth rate was obtained from photographs taken at regular time intervals. Analysis of the results was carried out by assuming that these surface cracks behaved as semi-elliptical surface flaws and applying linear elastic fracture mechanics theory. The analysis demonstrated that the method could produce valid stress intensity/crack growth rate data at lower crack velocities than reported previously. However, from a statistical point of view, the monitoring of only one relatively small area of the surface of a composite is not sufficiently representative of the surface as a whole. Also the limited number of cracks which could be monitored gave rise to problems in the calculation of the stress intensity. This was mainly due to coalescence of growing cracks, resulting in a sudden change in the aspect ratio thereby markedly affecting the growth rate.

In this paper we describe the use of a programmable photomicroscope to monitor a comparatively large surface area of the composites with a consequent improvement in the accuracy of the stress intensity/crack growth rate data and its extension to the rate of nucleation.

Experimental Techniques

The vacuum impregnation technique fully described in detail in reference (2) was used to fabricate 0° unidirectional epoxy glass composites. The matrix resin was Epikote 828 cured with 80 phr Epikure NMA and 1.5 phr BDMA (Shell Ltd). The reinforcement was Silenka 084P, E-glass roving (1200 Tex). Specimens in the form of coupons were cut from the laminate using a water cooled diamond wheel, and postcured at 150°C for 3 hours. The polyester composites were fabricated as described in reference 3. The matrix resin was Crystic 272 cured using 2 phr catalyst M(MEKP) and 0.25 phr accelerator E (cobalt soap), Scott-Bader and Co. Ltd. After 24 hours at room temperature the specimens were cut from the laminate as above and cured at 130°C for 2 hours. Specimens for characterisation by tensile testing had adhered aluminium end-tags. Measurements of strain were made using polyester fibre strain gauges bonded to the specimen face.

For the stress corrosion experiments, the unidirectional specimens were maintained under conditions of uniaxial tension at constant load by means of an Instron Universal Testing Machine (1196) with constant load facility. The aqueous acidic environment ($0.5\text{M H}_2\text{SO}_4$) was contained in a rectangular glass cell with optically flat sides attached to the specimen by means of a stainless steel clamp. Leakproof seals were made using RTV silicone rubber. In the experiments with the glass-polyester samples the cut edges were sealed with a layer of cold-cured epoxy resin (Araldite from Ciba-Geigy) and a layer of the silicone rubber.

Observations on the nucleation and growth of the surface cracks was carried out by mean of the automated photomicroscope shown in Figure 1. This consisted of an Olympus photomicroscope mounted on a mechanical stage which could move in the two planes parallel to the specimen face. Movement of the photomicroscope was controlled by a microprocessor with software designed to store the coordinate of the areas to be monitored, the residence time at each position, the number of complete cycles through the specified sequence, and the delay between each cycle. At each position a photographic record of the surface of the specimen was taken. In the Mk 1 photomicroscope, a 35 mm SLR camera with motor drive was used. However this proved to be unsuitable because of the large amount of photographic processing, manual measurement and cataloguing involved. In the Mk 2 photomicroscope the SLR camera was replaced by a CCTV camera and associated digitising equipment (Digithurst Ltd) to allow the pictures to be stored on floppy disks. The digitised pictures were then transferred to the university's mainframe computer for processing by specifically written image processing software. Basically this programme recognises the cracks from their aspect ratio and uses the last picture of each sequence as a master on which all of the cracks are numbered. It then relocates the previous picture of the sequence onto the master picture. Since the photomicroscope may not return precisely to the original position, a pattern recognition subroutine has been included to give the best fit between the previous image. Once the necessary off-set coordinates have been obtained it is possible to identify each of the cracks with its counterpart in the master picture and its length measured and stored. This procedure is carried out for every picture in each sequence of the total group. The results consist of a sequential list of numbered cracks together with their length at each of the predetermined time intervals. In order to determine the crack growth

Figure 1 - Programmable photomicroscope with digitising facility (Mk II) showing CCTV, photomicroscope and microprocessors.

Figure 2 - Macrophotographs of large stress corrosion surface cracks showing their semi-circular shape (1) oblique view of specimen, (2) side view, A illuminated for maximum scatter, (3) plan view, B, (4) geometry of an elliptical crack.

rate the cracks were sorted into categories of length and averaged per unit time.

Optical microscopy was carried out on sectioned coupons to determine the aspect ratio of the surface cracks. However because of the limited depth of field available in a microscope, photographs of cracks at various angles were obtained using a 35mm camera with a macro lens attachment.

Results and Discussion

Using the analysis of Irwin (see reference 7) the stress intensity around the periphery of the elliptical flaw (Figure 2) is given by equation 1.

$$K_1 = \frac{\sigma(\pi a)^{\frac{1}{2}}}{\phi} \left(\sin^2 \phi + \frac{a^2}{c^2} \cos^2 \phi \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad (1)$$

where σ is the applied stress, a and c are the semi-major and semi-minor axes of the ellipse respectively, ϕ is the angle from the major axis and ϕ is an elliptical integral given by

$$\phi = \int_0^{\pi/2} \left[1 - \left(\frac{c^2 - a^2}{c^2} \right) \sin^2 \phi \right]^{\frac{1}{2}} \delta \phi \quad (2)$$

Equation 1 predicts that the stress intensity K_1 is a maximum at the end of the minor axis. This implies that in the absence of any other factors, elliptical surface flaws will maintain a semicircular shape. Optical examination of polished sections from stress corroded samples confirms that the shape of the surface cracks are approximately semicircular as shown in Figure 2. In this study we are only concerned with the stress intensity at the ends of the c-axis, since this controls the rate of growth parallel to the surface. Corrections have to be applied to equation 1 when dealing with specimens of finite dimensions. The correction for the back free surface amounts to an increase in K_1 by $\approx 12\%$. The front free surface correction is dependent on the aspect ratio of the crack, and the ratio of crack depth to specimen thickness. Therefore, providing only small cracks of aspect ratio no greater than 1:2 (a:c) are considered, the correction becomes minimal and is ignored in this work. A further correction for the plastic deformation at the crack tip must also be taken into account. Equation 3 shows the corrected form of equation (1).

$$K_1 (\phi = 0) = 1.12 \sigma \left(\pi \frac{a}{Q} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad (3)$$

where Q is known as the shape parameter and contains the plastic deformation correction.

$$Q = (\phi^2 - 0.212 \sigma^2 / \sigma_y^2)^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad (4)$$

Assuming the yield stress to be near its fracture stress, then $\sigma / \sigma_y = 1$, which produces a small error in Q .

The applicability of using this theoretical approach to obtain the magnitude of K_1 has already been shown in a previous paper (6). Although the general trend in those results was consistent with previous work (3)

Figure 3 - A comparison of the crack growth rates in epoxy GRP obtained from the static photomicroscope at an initial applied strain of 0.5% (□) and the Mk I programmable photomicroscope at 0.4% (●).

there was an unacceptable degree of scatter. This was considered to be in part a result of the limited sample size inherent in using a static photomicroscope. One of the principal aims behind the design of the programmable photomicroscope was to enable a comparatively large area of the surface of the specimen to be monitored so that more representative data of the dependence of crack growth rate on crack length could be obtained. In Figure 3 a comparison between the results obtained with the static photomicroscope and the Mk I programmable photomicroscope are shown. The overall vertical displacement of the two sets of data results from the differing initial applied stresses. The results from the Mk I programmable photomicroscope shown in Figure 3 were obtained from 14 individual locations of approximate dimensions 2 mm x 1.3 mm in which >1500 determinations of the crack growth rate were computed.

It has been reported that over a limited range of crack growth rate, it is related to the stress intensity factor K_I according to equation 5.

$$\frac{dc}{dt} = \alpha K_I^n \quad (5)$$

Figure 4 - The crack growth data in Figure 3 as a function of stress intensity

Therefore a linear relationship between log crack growth rate and log K_1 , should exist. Figure 4 shows such a plot for the data shown in Figure 3. The two sets of data show a good degree of coincidence, demonstrating that the use of stress intensity factors normalises both groups of data at differing applied strain effectively. However the scatter in the data from the static photomicroscope is not reduced significantly.

In Figure 5 a comparison between the results obtained by the Mk I and Mk II photomicroscopes are shown. Those for the Mk II were obtained from 28 separate areas of the specimen surface in which over 100 cracks were observed. It should be noted that the field of view of the digital camera is less than the 35 mm SLR camera, and that even though more individual fields of view could be monitored the total surface area was less. For the SLR camera it was $\approx 35 \text{ mm}^2$ whereas for the Mk II digital camera it was only $\approx 11.5 \text{ mm}^2$. Good coincidence is seen between the results obtained with the Mk I and Mk II programmable photomicroscopes. Also shown in Figure 5 are curves for data obtained by Aveston and Sillwood (4) and Price and Hull (5) for polyester composites. The data for the epoxy composite shows larger

Figure 5 - Crack growth rate against stress intensity for epoxy GRP. Mk I (○), Mk II (*). The initial applied strains were 0.4% and 0.5% respectively. The continuous and dashed lines are for polyester GRP from Price and Hull (5) and Aveston and Sillwood (4) respectively.

crack growth rates than the polyester system at similar values of stress intensity. This is in agreement with the poor stress corrosion resistance of the epoxy composite which has been discussed in detail elsewhere (2,3). These differences are also apparent in Figure 6 where a comparison of the crack nucleation rates for polyester and epoxy composites is shown. Although the applied stress on the polyester composite is considerably greater than that on the epoxy, the form of the two curves is totally different and reflects the different behaviour of these composites under stress corrosion conditions. Both curves show an initial increasing rate reaching a maximum after a few minutes. This is probably associated with the rapid stress corrosion failure of exposed and possibly predamaged glass at or near the surface of the laminate. The difference between the initial maximum nucleation rates results from the much greater load on the polyester specimen. After this rise in nucleation rate, a steady decline is observed for the polyester composite. In contrast, the epoxy composite exhibits a short induction period followed by an exponential increase in the rate of nucleation. These cracks also behave differently in that they easily propagate through the matrix, whereas in the polyester composite they

Figure 6 - The rate of nucleation of stress corrosion surface cracks in GRP Epoxy at 0.4% strain (●), polyester at 1.1% strain (□).

showed no inclination to propagate. However, propagation can be observed at applied stresses of greater than 443 MNM² (equivalent to initial applied strain of 1.4%).

These experiments demonstrate the validity of applying linear elastic fracture mechanics to the growth of stress corrosion induced surface cracks. By using a sophisticated monitoring technique the nucleation rates can also be obtained. Whilst recognising the role of the matrix fracture toughness it is also apparent that the mechanism of diffusion of the environment differs for the two composites. We have previously reported (3) that particularly in the case of the epoxy glass composite, the resin-fibre interface may be rather susceptible to stress corrosion to form debonds which act as capillaries for transport of the acidic media. For the cracks to grow in a brittle manner as shown in Figure 2 and implicit in the LEFM analysis used, we conclude that the fibres must be well bonded to matrix and that these capillaries are formed by debonding over a small fraction of the fibre surface.

Conclusions

Under acidic stress corrosion conditions, cracks form in the surface of E-glass fibre composites. These cracks have been shown to maintain a semi-circular shape and to grow in a brittle manner. It has proved possible therefore, to apply linear elastic fracture mechanics to obtain stress intensity data. The major drawbacks of crack interference and local variations in the composite microstructure, such as fibre volume fraction, have been overcome by monitoring a large number of cracks by using a programmable photomicroscope. There are three major advantages of this technique. Firstly, the rates of crack nucleation can be measured. Secondly, there is the opportunity to monitor extremely low rates of crack growth. Thirdly the difficulties associated with a complicated specimen geometry can be circumvented.

The large differences in both the nucleation and growth rates for the polyester and epoxy composites demonstrate the need to quantify both stages of the stress corrosion mechanism.

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